

FOODITY

PhotoVoice

Workshops

FOODITY

Funded by
the European Union

Results of the workshops on citizens' perception of data privacy and data sovereignty linked to food and nutrition.

Austria | Bulgaria | Portugal | 2023

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**At
FOODITY,
we are on a
mission**

We are focused on creating a vibrant European ecosystem of digital solutions for food and nutrition that respect individual's right to personal data sovereignty — and demonstrate the potential of data-driven innovations while engaging citizens in their development.

The FOODITY PhotoVoice Workshops

Involving
citizens in
creating better
food systems

In the summer of 2023, FOODITY partners hosted three workshops across Europe to discuss **data privacy and sovereignty in food and nutrition** with a diverse group of citizens.

Guided by Caroline Wang's PhotoVoice method, aimed at empowering individuals to engage in community conversations and decisions, **participants seized the power of photography to share their stories, concerns and desires.**

These workshops facilitated discussions and provided ideas on **how citizens can control their personal food and nutrition data.** They also ignited conversations about how better data handling and controlled usage can promote **healthier and more sustainable lifestyles,** ultimately fostering the development of **improved food systems.**

On the next pages, **discover the key insights that emerged** and learn how taking control of food and nutrition data can lead to a better future for all.

The Workshop Hubs

Austria

Led by the Centre for
Social Innovation (ZSI)

Portugal

Led by F6S

Bulgaria

Led by JIBE company

ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE INNOVATION
CENTRE FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION

J I B E

AGENDA TAG 1

- 14:30 Willkommen
- 15:00 Kennenlernen
- 15:30 Rekrutierung & Nachhaltigkeit
- 16:00 Wie Tiere Zusammenarbeiten
- 16:05 Fakten & Hintergrundwissen
- 17:00 Zusammenfassung & Austausch
- 17:30 Abschlussrunde

AGENDA TAG 2

- 10:30 Willkommen
- 11:00 Reflexion
- 11:05 Arbeit in Teams
- 11:30 Gruppenarbeit
- 12:00 Zusammenfassung & Austausch

AGENDA TAG 3

- 10:30 Willkommen
- 11:00 Zusammenfassung & Austausch
- 11:30 Zusammenfassung & Austausch
- 12:00 Zusammenfassung & Austausch

Austria Hub

Led by the Centre for
Social Innovation (ZSI)

Organisers:

- **Ilse Marschalek**
- **Maria Schrammel**

ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE INNOVATION
CENTRE FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION

Health

Eating a variety of appealing and tasty foods is crucial for staying healthy.

What's considered healthy varies from person to person, so it's important to find what works for you.

Self determination/autonomy

We deserve control over our own information and decisions. We prefer not to be told what to do, especially regarding our personal data and privacy.

Framework for data collection

Data collection can be beneficial if done safely and securely. Knowing who owns our data and trusting its protection is essential.

Knowledge exchange

Food labels must be clear and trustworthy to help us make informed choices.

We need easy access to food information, even in places like doctor's offices.

Knowing if our food is local and in season is also essential.

Networking/ cross-linking

We should be free to choose
whom we share our data with
and feel confident in doing so.

Building trustworthy
communities can facilitate
data sharing and better
decision-making.

HOW
NOT
TO
DIE

Awareness raising and education

Learning about where our food comes from and thinking critically about what we eat is vital for our health and the planet's health.

Starting this learning early and sharing traditional knowledge about nutrition is important for everyone.

Portugal Hub

Led by FS6

Organisers:

- **Samuel Almeida**
- **António Damasceno**

ontabilidade e
apuramento de IRS e
Salários
Relatórios económicos
Apoio à gestão

Individual responsibility

Take responsibility for your data and be mindful of what you share and with whom.

It is acceptable not to follow the herd and to make your own individual choices.

Consumer profile

Your food and product choices draw up your individual consumer profile.

This is important information for you as a citizen, but also highly valuable data to other organisations to deliver customised content.

Control paradox

Look to take control of your choices related to food and personal data.

Empower yourself by evaluating your options and making informed decisions.

Data-driven opportunities

Be conscious of the data you share and with whom you share it, but also be mindful of the opportunities that data can provide to citizens and the food and nutrition industry.

Bulgaria Hub

Led by JIBE company

Organisers:

- **Hans Houf**
- **Carolina Gogova**

J I B E

What is healthy?

Clearer and more consistent guidelines on how to pick the right diet for us and our children, what truly is healthy and how to navigate the abundance of choices in the supermarket presents a difficulty for most people, confused by the conflicting information found online.

What do the labels mean?!

Very few seem to know the answer, and everyone agrees that the information could be presented in a better way.

Although steps have been taken in this direction, the disconnect remains.

“Our data should work for us”

While some are more reluctant to share their data than others, users agree their data should be used to benefit them and society at large, and measures should be taken to prevent that data from being misused and exploited.

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